

DETERMINING CHALLENGES OF DIGITAL MARKETING MANAGEMENT IN DEVELOPING YOUTH ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND CREATIVITY

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to identify the challenges of digital marketing management in fostering youth entrepreneurship and creativity in Tanzania. The low level of digital marketing in Tanzania, due to various challenges, has attracted a researcher in this particular field of study. Customers in the market use digital information to understand the goods and services offered by multiple businesses, organizations, and individuals worldwide. Digital marketing transformation is not limited to developed countries or the world, but also applies to Africa and Tanzania, in particular. Tanzania initiated the Information and Communication Technology Policy (ICTT) to facilitate the business transformation from Traditional to Digital. The findings indicate that digital marketing has a positive impact on the development of youth entrepreneurship, primarily through social media and websites.

Keywords: Digital Marketing, Entrepreneurship, Youth Entrepreneurs, and Creativity.

1. INTRODUCTION

The growth of technology and the broader dissemination of information through the internet and various platforms, such as social media, smartphones, and electronic word of mouth, has taken the world by surprise (Al-Emran & Malik, 2016). The advancement in technology has made the world appear like a single village. In the market, customers utilize digital information to understand the products and services offered by various companies and organizations worldwide, where information and experience sharing have become integral to daily life (Stephen, 2016). It is estimated that one-third of global advertising spending in 2020 was allocated to digital marketing channels. This situation can imply that consumer marketing in the future will be fully implemented in a digital environment, especially in social media and other digital platforms (Salloum & Shaalan, 2018)

Figure 1 below illustrates the global landscape of digital technology. The world seems to be a small ball where one can use only a minute to revolve it. No matter how far away the place, one can use a minute to send or receive information and communicate face-to-face. Digital technology has made communication easier for people on every continent, whether from Europe, Asia, Africa, or the Americas.

Digital Technology in the World

Figure 1: Retrieved from twitter.com/machingatz/status/1439323346890547217/photo/4. (22.04.2023)

Currently, Digital Marketing Management is a growing trend worldwide and is applied in almost all sectors of the economy. Essentially, digital marketing/e-marketing enables the simultaneous access to information of various customers, providing broader coverage of goods and services at a global level. Moreover, digital marketing helps eliminate the challenges associated with geographical locations, enabling different producers and sellers to attract and retain customers from anywhere in the world (Boone & Hendricks, 2014). In addition to the above, digital marketing facilitates the easy procurement of equipment with minimal or no corruption tendency, a characteristic often lacking in the public sector of developing countries (Andrews, Criscuolo, and Gal, 2015). Rationally, 87.7% of people in Europe have access to the internet, which accounts for approximately 16% of the global internet use. The global average is 58.8%. For example, in Montenegro in January 2020, social media had 381,800 Facebook users, which represents approximately 67% of the population. Digital marketing contributes to the development of firms' operations from both operational and economic perspectives. Digital marketing has a wide range of impacts on business performance; however, there is a lack of research on what explicitly influences the application of digital marketing, particularly in Montenegro (Melovic, 2020).

Today, there are over 500 million members on social networking platforms, of which 60 per cent are affluent consumers in the United States. According to a recent Wealth Survey

from the Luxury Institute, the USA has consumers with an average income of \$287,000 (Mathieson, 2010) In Africa, young people are a crucial group in driving economic development. Nowadays, most of them have access to digital technology. If they can utilise this technology effectively in the economy, such as e-marketing and e-procurement in Entrepreneurship, the outcome for the national economy will be positive. Although some youths use digital technology for non-economic matters, such as terrorism, sending greetings, playing games, and watching movies or music on Netflix or YouTube. For the prosperity of youth Entrepreneurship and national economy, the governments need to create good internet infrastructure, good digital policies, and a good education curriculum that includes digital lessons (Kelimanzila, J. 2021)

Table 1: Retrieved from www.internetworldstats.com (2022)

AFRICA 2022 POPULATION AND INTERNET USERS' STATISTICS						
Africa	Population (2022 Est.)	Internet Users 31-DEC-2000	Internet Users 31-DEC-21	Internet Penetration	Internet Growth % 2000 - 2021	Facebook subscribers 30-APRIL-22
Algeria	45,150,879	50,000	37,836,425	83.8%	50,756 %	26,291,400
Cameroon	27,646,656	20,000	9,158,422	33.1%	39,292 %	4,723,600
Central African	4,967,426	1,500	557,085	11.2%	37,039 %	150,000
Egypt	105,530,371	450,000	54,741,493	51.9 %	12,064 %	51,286,200
Ethiopia	119,748,379	10,000	21,147,255	17.7 %	211,372 %	7,535,700
Ghana	32,154,245	30,000	14,767,818	45.9 %	49,126 %	9,163,200
Kenya	55,752,020	200,000	46,870,422	85.2 %	23,335 %	12,445,700
Madagascar	28,427,328	30,000	2,864,000	10.1 %	9,446 %	2,864,000
Malawi	19,647,684	15,000	2,717,243	13.8 %	18,015 %	637,600
Morocco	37,344,795	100,000	25,589,581	68.5 %	25,489 %	21,730,000
Nigeria	211,400,708	200,000	154,301,195	73.0 %	101,484 %	31,860,000
Rwanda	13,276,513	5,000	5,981,638	45.1 %	119,532 %	806,200
South Africa	60,041,994	2,400,000	34,545,165	57.5 %	1,339 %	24,600,000
Tanzania	61,498,437	115,000	23,142,960	37.6 %	20,024 %	5,223,000
Uganda	47,123,531	40,000	18,502,166	39.3 %	46,155 %	3,328,000
Western Sahara	611,875	n/a	28,000	4.6 %	n/a	27,000
Zambia	18,920,651	20,000	9,870,427	52.2 %	49,252 %	2,543,000
Zimbabwe	15,092,171	50,000	8,400,000	55.7 %	16,700 %	1,303,000

The table above presents examples of population size and Internet user numbers for several African countries from 2000 to 2022, along with the Internet growth rate and the number of Facebook subscribers. The table confirms that the use of digital marketing in Tanzania and other African countries remains low, as it indicates a total population of 61,498,437 in 2022. In contrast, in 2000, there were only 115,000 internet users, and as of December 31, 2021, the number had increased to 23,142,960.

Internet penetration is 37%, internet growth is 20,024% and Facebook subscribers are 5,223,000. Low level of internet users or internet subscribers, slow internet penetration, and internet growth compared to other African countries like South Africa, Nigeria, Kenya, Morocco, Egypt, and Algeria can be caused by several factors, for example, the cost of digital equipment, In Tanzania, many Entrepreneurs are still conducting their businesses

traditionally, waiting for buyers at their business locations. Instead, the other marketers are suffering from the decline in their business revenue due to a decrease in sales of their products or goods and services (Kimicho, 2020). According to al. (2006), it is therefore important to consider procurement as key to the performance of Entrepreneurship in Tanzania. For example, entrepreneurs can order products online from well-verified sources, and all transactions are transparent and well-documented. However, despite the government's effort to promote e-marketing in procurement, the use of Digital marketing in Tanzania is low due to slow internet, limited coverage, outdated files online, illiteracy, and conservatism of people who prefer hard copies compared to soft copies (Kaaya & Assey, 2016)

Entrepreneurs (Machinga) in Dar Es Salaam City, Tanzania

Figure 2: Retrieved from <https://www.rifs-potsdam.de> (22.04.2023)

The figure illustrates how some entrepreneurs in Tanzania continue to operate their businesses traditionally, contributing to the fact that Digital marketing in Tanzania remains low. The effects lead to slow economic development. As it is time-consuming, and weather changes, such as rain and sun, may hinder marketing efforts. Additionally, congestion may lead to theft, death, and injuries to customers. The Second Five Years Development Plan (FYDP II) was initiated in Tanzania since 2016 in order to influence the progress of the clear mission of the Tanzania Development Vision (TDV) from now to 2025 as a long-term vision of transforming the country from small scale production in agricultural economy to the large technological based economy and semi-industrialized economy by 2025.

Digital marketing facilitates the discovery of key elements of economic development. This is clearly stated in the National Information Communication Technology (ICT) Policy of 2016, which gives a basis or framework for the growth of ICT platforms in Tanzania, whereas it acts as a vital factor for social and economic prosperity in the country (GSM Association, 2019)

In recent years, Tanzania has been working hard to make sure its investment in fibre infrastructure. The Tanzanian government considered and introduced the National ICT Broadband Backbone (NICTBB), which spans over 7,500 km throughout the country, covering both regions and districts. The fiber consisted of Airtel, Tigo, Vodacom, and Zantel, comprising approximately 400 km of metro fiber in Dar es Salaam, Dodoma, Morogoro, Mwanza, and Arusha, as well as over 1,500 km of backbone fiber connecting the major cities of Dar es Salaam, Dodoma, Arusha, and Moshi. Even though the existence of mobile technology has contributed to digital transformation in the country. Tanzania's mobile market comprises eight mobile operators, underscoring its position as one of the most competitive markets in Sub-Saharan Africa (GSM Association, 2019). In Tanzania, the use of e-marketing has significantly improved, as noted by Kaaya and Assey (2016), who reported that 0.5% of the population uses the internet, which is higher than the 0.3% in Uganda. The government has demonstrated its commitment to the development of ICT transport and implemented the National ICT policy, which has enabled the government to improve telecommunications, infrastructure, and the use of ICT in service delivery (Wangwe, 2010). Furthermore, ICT covers 50% of the landmass in Tanzania and 75% of the population uses ICT on daily basis and to make ICT more accessible the government has extended 10,000 kilometers of fiber capable to reduce ICT divide between the Urban and the rural and also established Universal communication service Access fund (UCSAF) which targets ICT in viable economic projects in the country (Wangwe, 2010), Generally, to have the right to speak about this study, "Digital Marketing Management in Developing Entrepreneurship in Tanzania", research must be done. Moreover, its success of can be achieved only if three important issues that underlie the effectiveness of the Dissertation are considered, namely, conceptual issues, Empirical issues, and methodological issues.

1.1 Problem Formulation

The Tanzanian government has implemented several initiatives to enhance the telecommunications and ICT environment. In 2003, the government formulated the National ICT policy with the primary objective of enhancing telecommunication and ICT infrastructure to promote e-marketing in the country (Wangwe, 2010). Moreover, the country has been experiencing an improvement in internet coverage (Kaaya & Assey, 2014). The government also issued e-governance guidelines in 2017 that the public sector should follow. According to Kowero (2012), these guidelines also revealed government efforts to promote e-marketing by spending over 250 billion Tanzanian shillings to establish a National Fiber Optic cable network, connecting all regions of the country. The government further established the e-Government Agency under the Executive Agencies Act. 30. 1997 Cap 245, which is a semi-autonomous institution under the President's Office, Public Service Management, and the e-Government Act No. 10, 2019. These government efforts aim to promote efficiency in all public institutions, enabling them to serve citizens better, faster, and provide quality service to all (eGA, 2012). In Tanzania, specifically urban areas, the Entrepreneurs who are named 'Machinga', a few of them use Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, YouTube, and Websites for marketing their businesses. There is no wide range of use of Digital technology due

to; High price of digital instruments, like; Smart-phones, Laptops and desktops, High price of internet bundle, Weak internet connection, negative attitude and intention of using digital technology for marketing (they have not given awareness of believing that digital technology can be used for marketing) and lack of knowledge of using Digital technology. Entrepreneurs in rural areas they are still using traditional ways of marketing, as far as Digital technology is not yet widespread enough to adapt.

1.2 Research objective

The objective of the Study means the aim or purpose for which questions are answered through the use of scientific procedures. Each research study has its specific purpose; for Example, to be familiar with the phenomenon, discovering the accurate features/characteristics of a particular individual/matter, testing the hypothesis of a particular problem (Gilakjan, 2012; Kothari, 2004). Nevertheless, it is the answer to the research problem. The general objective of this study is to determine the challenges facing Digital Marketing Management in the development of youth Entrepreneurship in Tanzania. The general objective of this study is to determine the challenges facing Digital Marketing Management in the development of youth Entrepreneurship in Tanzania.

1.3 Research Questions

Research Questions are the focused questions around the study, with the aim of answering the researcher's goals. They are answered critically in chapter four of the research through: the data analysis, presentation and discussion of data. Generally, Research Questions follows after Research Objectives. The following are the research questions:

- 1.3.1 What do the Youth Entrepreneurs in Tanzania employ the forms of Digital Marketing?
- 1.3.2 What are the digital marketing management practices adopted in Tanzanian?
- 1.3.3 To what extent does digital marketing management has influenced the development of youth Entrepreneurship in Tanzania?
- 1.3.4 What are the challenges faced by Entrepreneurs, Customers and Tanzanian government in Digital marketing management towards Entrepreneurship development in Tanzania?
- 1.3.5 What are the ways forward for the experienced Challenges by Entrepreneurs, Customers and Tanzanian government in Digital marketing management towards Entrepreneurship development in Tanzania?

1.4 Specific objectives of the study

Specific Objectives are statements to which the strong interest of the researcher base. They specify aims that the researcher plans to achieve in a study. Research Objectives are found after the statement of the problem (Creswell, 2014). In a real sense they define the hypothesis of the search.

The specific Objectives of the study are as follows;

- 1.4.1 To analyze various forms of digital marketing adopted by Tanzanians towards the development of youth Entrepreneurship
- 1.4.2 To analyze different digital marketing management practices adopted by Tanzanians in developing youth Entrepreneurship
- 1.4.3 To examine the extent to which digital marketing management has influenced the development of youth Entrepreneurship in Tanzania
- 1.4.4 To examine challenges faced by Tanzanian government and Entrepreneurs in Digital marketing management towards youth Entrepreneurship development
- 1.4.5 To analyze ways forward for the experienced challenges by Tanzanian government and Entrepreneurs in Digital marketing management towards youth Entrepreneurship development

1.5 Authenticity and Decency of Research

This study will be done by the researcher and all cited authors will be acknowledged on the text and reference. The work will be well checked for plagiarism and any other academic rules of the university and other research bodies will be abided all the time during the study. Generally, significant number of papers have analyzed the role of digital marketing and the effects of DCM on purchase intention like; (Lou and Xie, 2020; Yaghin, Safarzadeh and Karimi, 2020; Febrian et al, 2021) in modern business but none of similar research has thus far been conducted in Tanzania a country in economic transition. Whereas the researcher has decided to conduct the study which assesses on how digital marketing management can develop entrepreneurship in Tanzania unlike the aforementioned studies.

1.6 Contribution of Research

Digital marketing has created several opportunities in the procurement process, for example e-auctioning, e-bidding and e-procurement to Entrepreneurs. It has made the world to appear like a small village and has helped individuals to share the information easily on goods and services provided by different organizations. Moreover, this study will contribute to the society in the following areas;

1.6.1 Theoretical Contribution

This research aims to pave the way for creativity and thinking among various stakeholders on the use of e-marketing and e-procurement in online product and service purchases by organizations, customers, and Entrepreneurs in Tanzania. The results of this study are expected to generate more knowledge on the given theory and Conceptual Framework

1.6.2 Empirical Contribution

It will also contribute to the competitiveness of the Tanzanians organization and Entrepreneurs on the digital marketing and e-procurement from well-developed internet in the procurement process that has never experienced before.

The Tanzanians will now be able to use the information of the study to do business online and have products delivered to them on their doorsteps. The Tanzanian Entrepreneurs will learn on how to use social media to attract more customers on procurement of different products.

1.6.3 Policy Contribution

This Research will enable policy makers to issue the policy that will benefit the Tanzanian government, organizations, Entrepreneurs and customers. If the results of the study will confirm that, the use of digital marketing in procurement of products/goods and services is of more benefit than traditional/non digital, then the government will be in position to regulate policy that will strictly require the use of digital marketing.

1.6.4 Methodological Contribution

The results of the research are expected to improve research methodologies that explain the existing phenomenon and samples. The study will adopt quantitative approach by using a descriptive research design to various stakeholders of Digital Marketing in Tanzania. The specifically designed questionnaires will be given to respondents who will be selected by using the Morgan table at a confidence level, and some of the questionnaires will be administered online. The analysis of data will be done by using SAS program which is not much used in Tanzania. Pretesting and Piloting of samples will be done for validity and reliability. All these methodological gaps will provide the Beneficiaries of this study more knowledge of conducting valid and reliable dissertations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The chapter demonstrates numerous ideas regarding digital marketing drawn from diverse secondary sources of information and how they relate to the problem of study. Reviews of Marketing, Digital Marketing, Digital Marketing Management, Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurship Development, Digital Marketing Management Practices, Forms of Digital Marketing, Digital Marketing Management Influence in Developing Entrepreneurship, Challenges Faced in Digital Marketing Management towards Entrepreneurship Development, and Ways to Overcome Experienced Challenges in Digital Marketing Management towards Entrepreneurship Development are all included. In the united kingdom the digitization of procurement process yielded several benefits in public sector such as procurement becoming strategically in decision making, effectiveness and efficiency, profitability and helped in supporting new business models (Bienhaus and Haddud 2018).

OECD, (2011) explained that e-procurement in digital marketing has promoted automation of requisition, approval and order management of goods and services through internet-based protocol in United States and Germany public service. Ramamoorthi and Appasamy (2015) explained that E-marketing has promoted e-auction offer, time of action, bid price, knowledge, payment, and delivery of the successful bids on selected items in India. The implementation of digital marketing is more broadly carried out by the Entrepreneurs in development of e-business as a positive consequence for the

relationship between Entrepreneurs and consumers (Leimstoll et al, 2018; Garzella et al, 2021). The results of data from a survey done in America 2016 on marketer e-commerce Pulizzi and Handley, (2017) reveal that, 89% of marketers now use content marketing, and 88% consider it an important component of their marketing program. There are some e-commerce companies which entered into the ranking of the world in private companies with the value of over \$1 billion in April 2020. Example, The Business growth though digital marketing in Indonesia shows good progress. Kominfo, (2020) predicted that by 2020 it will reach an evaluation of USD 130 billion with an annual growth rate of 50 percent. Marketers must create campaigns, content or layout on application of e-commerce which is more accessible so that consumer confidence increases in using e-commerce through websites. The perceived benefits have a positive effect on consumer attitudes and intentions (Lestari, 2019) Each country has different ways of customers self-actualize which involve the use website, because of cultural differences (Hofstede and Bond, 1988; Valaei et al., 2016).

Studies previously indicated that Asian consumers are more likely to prefer spread negative EWOM information than Western consumers about service failure (Liu and McClure, 2001; Chan and Wan, 2008). This behavior might be the reason that different countries will have different ways to communicate. Then marketers must adopt marketing strategies that are different for different countries (Zhu, Ye and Chang, 2017). This is because group members based on the same age who share the same values, experiences, and preferences will have greater influence on deciding what to purchase and how (Parment, 2013). In retail trade, it is recognized that there is a stark difference between generations of groups. Thus, the analysis of various features patterns, personality and its effects across generations is very important to be able to understand consumer behavior (Lissitsa and Kol, 2019). In the context of consumers, they will significantly influence purchasing patterns and shopping behavior. This assumption is used as a general basis for segmenting consumers (Parment, 2013; Chaney, Touzani and Slimane, 2017).

Stokes and Lomax, (2012) conducted a study on the impacts of social media marketing towards marketing performance in Canada. The important areas studied were the digital platforms utilized and the challenges of applying them. It was found that the most digital platforms applied were; direct mailing, social media as well as websites. The digital marketing has significant effect on getting near to customers in business, in large extent the geographical coverage is larger compared to traditional marketing, feedback is easily given and price transparency. The research observed only the overall digital marketing but did not observe on social media as one aspect of digital marketing. The study by Oni, Shumba and Matiza (2014) in Polokwane South Africa on Assessing the impact of Social media based marketing on the turnover of retailers showed that the majority of retailers in Polokwane used social media. This had positive results in reaching many customers, selling and marketing of their products and thus increased the sales turnovers of the specific retailers. In Tanzania there is small number of studies that have speculated on Digital Marketing Communications, many of the researches were conducted on the "Use of Electronic Mobile as Part of the Digital Marketing".

The study, "Impact of Digital Marketing on Business Performances in Online Food Marketing and Telecommunication Industries: The Case of Dar Es Salaam, Tanzania," was conducted by Chille, (2018). The purpose of the study was to determine how digital marketing affected Dar es Salaam businesses: Jumia Food Tanzania Limited, an online food retailer, and Vodacom Tanzania Limited, a mobile phone provider. Hatibu, (2017) assessed the effects of social media on small and medium enterprises development in Tanzania particularly in Kinondoni District. This research was carried out with three objectives which were; to identify the impact of social media on the market accessibility of SMEs in Kinondoni district, the impact of social media on the pricing of products from SMEs in Kinondoni district and the challenges encountered by the small and medium enterprises in the adoption of social media in Kinondoni district. The researcher concluded that many of SMEs in Kinondoni Municipal do their business on cosmetics and clothing and they have registered their business to social media platforms, like, Instagram, WhatsApp and Facebook. Many of SMEs use more than 5 hours to explore on social media platforms.

SMEs which have their pages on social media have 1-4 employees with less than Tsh: 5,000,000/= as invested capital. The use of social media by SMEs has built effective relationship with their customers and they can be reached easily. This has facilitated easy coverage of larger geographical locations. Furthermore, both SMEs and Customers can easily get feedback on business online, example, what customers like or dislike. Moreover, there are a several challenges encountered by SMEs on the use of social media like, human resource challenges, reputational challenges and network brake down challenges. Hence the study did not look on the impact of social media marketing on SMEs development. It was found that the majority of respondents agreed to use social media sites like Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube, marketing websites like trip advisor and booking.com, mobile applications, and corporate websites to help businesses spread awareness of their services and products in their target market, according to (Kimicho, 2020). Hill, (2015) conducted a study on the effects of ICT adoption on the performance of SMEs in Tanzania a case of Mwanza district. The results of the research show that only few of SMEs have experience about the application of social media together with their benefits.

Many of SMEs have been applying the internet just for location and contract purpose. Most of the SMEs have portrayed a positive exhibition and different benefits by using ICT in their Entrepreneurship. The following were the challenges towards the application of ICT; Absence of inward abilities, absence of budgetary help, non-accessibility of foundation and individual reasons. Storey, (2014) the study explored the link between ICT and SMEs in various areas of Tanzania. The assessment was based on literature review in order to see direct and indirect effects of ICT on SMEs development. Results of this research work found that ICT has effects on the development of external and internal communication and that for good performance it is significant to outline ICT investments and internal abilities and company processes. Technology itself is not as vital as the induced socio-economic improvement. Generally, the research observed on ICT and SMEs performance but did observe effectively on social media marketing on SMEs.

The majority of respondents agreed to use social media sites like Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube, marketing websites like TripAdvisor and booking.com, mobile applications, and corporate websites to help businesses spread awareness of their services and products in their target market, according to (Kimicho, 2020). Generally, most of studies have tried to speculate on the contribution of Digital Technology to Enterprises', Firms of business prosperity to some parts of countries but none of scholar or researcher has done the research of Digital Marketing Management in Developing Entrepreneurship in the whole country. This study will give out the general picture of Digital Marketing on Entrepreneurship development for the whole country of Tanzania. The study will find out how to manage Digital marketing in order to develop Entrepreneurship.

2.1 Thinking Framework

The conceptual framework is referred to as the methodology that presents the significant factors to be examined in the research in graphical or narrative form, as provided by (Fellows and Liu, 2003). However, Mugenda, (2003) stated that he described the conceptual framework as a collection of thoughts regarding relationships between study variables and illustrating these relationships graphically or diagrammatically. He continued by saying that conceptual frameworks show how the independent and dependent variables are thought to be related. In most cases, the thinking framework is wrapped into various theories, which ultimately produce the dissertation model as follows:

2.1.1 Diffusion of Innovation Theory

This important theory will support the study's conceptual framework and model. The theory was propounded by Rogers in 1962 at the University of New Mexico. The hypothesis of this theory explains how and why society and culture influenced the innovation of new technology. The innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority, and laggards are the main participants in this hypothesis. Knowing and promoting the use of modern technology (digital marketing) in the sale of goods and services is helpful in marketing. Marketers use the DIT extensively to encourage the adoption of their products. Although the theory faces difficulties in its application, this encourages the support of other Theories. For instance, the acceptance of new technology is heavily influenced by the level of education, and various civilizations have varying adoption rates (Halton, 2021)

2.1.2 The Uses and Gratification Theory (UGT)

Marketers have a responsibility to comprehend customer behavior in order to give consumers with relevant and valuable material, which is essential for the success of entrepreneurs. This can be accomplished by examining the factors that influence consumers' media consumption and decisions, which can be quantified using the universal gratification theory (UGT) (Lim and Ting, 2012; Huang, Bao and Li, 2017; Hollebeek and Macky, 2019; Pujadas-Hostench et al, 2019). This hypothesis has been used by (Lim and Ting, 2012; Yaoyuneyong et al. 2018; and Zhang et al, 2019) to analyze and explain online shopping behavior. UGT is therefore thought to be appropriate in determining consumers' views regarding entrepreneurs and media use.

UGT is used to explain the psychological requirements and social media, which can influence people's choices of particular media material, as well as the effects of media consumption, including attitudes and behavior (Ruggiero, 2000).

2.1.3 Relationship Marketing Theory (RMT)

Delivering information or messages to clients that can affect their behavior is what marketing communication is all about (Holliman and Rowley, 2014). Therefore, the business must be able to sustain consumer interactions in order to continue to work with affected brands to forge relationships based on trust (Taiminen and Ranaweera, 2019). Trust is the primary mediating variable from the existence of a stimulus carried out by Entrepreneurs and has implications for intention behavior that benefits marketers according to (Morgan and Hunt, 1994). The trust that consumers have in internet retailers is founded on their ability to communicate effectively with them. If the buyer perceives that the seller's communication through the website wasn't successful, they may hesitate to complete an online transaction because they may no longer trust e-commerce (Hajili, Sims, and Shanmugam, 2014; Chonget et al, 2018)

The qualities of ability, honesty, predictability, and goodness are all embodied in trust. Consumers are more willing to participate and transact on a website when they feel like they have earned that trust (McKnight and Chervany, 2001). Consumer trust in corporations that are accountable for their products is what is meant by this trust (Devos, Spini and Schwartz, 2002). Studies focusing on the internet have gained popularity across numerous academic disciplines since its inception. The concepts of confidence online and confidence offline are different. Because internet business owners and clients occasionally cannot meet in person, the online environment is frequently regarded as hazardous. When there is no trust, online marketing is more difficult to retain than it is offline, lack of trust is a significant obstacle to launching an internet business (Chang, Cheung and Tang, 2013). Concerns over the privacy of allegedly misused user data by one Indonesian e-commerce company led to a fall in confidence in 2019 (Wardoyo, 2020)

2.1.4 Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA)

According to (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1975), the most significant predictor of individual action is the desire to carry out the conduct. The individual's attitude toward the activity and the subjectivity of norms determines the behavior. They also demonstrate how individual attitudes toward activity include the conviction that a particular course of action will produce that outcome. More specifically, if someone feels that the result will benefit them, they are more likely to act in a certain way (Wu & Liu, 2007).

Swinyard (1993) describes that customer who have had a positive encounter with a product's appealing design will be considerably more likely to make a buy than customers who have had a negative one. After exploring a website, one's attitude toward using it is then regarded as an emotional assessment, whilst one's purchase intention refers to one's likelihood and willingness to make a purchase (Wu et al, 2013).

2.1.5 Generation of cohort Theory (GCT)

The theory emerged with differences in the content of formal education, socialization is influenced to a large extent by peer groups and experiences history of every generation (Ryder, 1965). A cohort is a group of people who were born at the same age. When they are teenagers, they tend to experience many external events which have effect in their social life that can influence their values, preferences, attitudes and buying behavior (Schewe & Meredith, 2004). GCT claims that their age mates can categorize the population. When the company can segment its cohort, it can help entrepreneurs of goods and services online to customize products and services, as well as design communication programs to attract consumer intention to buy products. Researchers have divided the times of birth of individuals into different generations: Generation Y, X, and Z. Each generation has different wants and needs, and also, they have different perceptions on the communication marketing strategy being done by Entrepreneurs. All these factors raise service quality and purchase intention (Chang et al., 2018).

Previous research has shown that Senior consumers behave and think differently than younger consumers (Lee, Cho, and Ahn, 2012). Between 1965 and 1980, Generation X was born (Smola & Sutton, 2002). Generation X believes that the views of others have a significant impact on decisions. They engage in consumer convenience through connections, make purchases, and act in ways that minimize risk. Those in the Generation Y age group were born between 1981 and 1995 (Brosdahl and Carpenter, 2011). The generation Z comes after Y. Many members of Generation Z are linked via smartphones and tablets, and they also have access to more information than members of previous generations do (Smith, 2019). According to APJII's research, generation Z prefers to do their business online. The generation Z purchases goods and services online, according to Lestari (2019), since they view websites as secured medium with minimal risk in comparison to traditional media. Tabassum, Khwaja, and Zaman, (2020) made the claim that Generation Z needs content that is delivered in a narrative, realistic, and engaging way in order to attract attitudes and emotions for them to be actively involved in the goals of Entrepreneurs. They achieved this by highlighting the positive characteristics of content under Generation Z. The primary characteristic of Generation Y is frequent use of technology (Immordino-Yang, Christodoulou, and Singh, 2012).

Generation Y regularly engages in social interactions through digital media, and they also enjoy using technology for entertainment. Some authors claim that because young people grew up with technology and the internet, they have more experience using it (San-Martn, Prodanova, and Jiménez, 2015). For instance, Generation Y users spend more time than Generation X users exploring the information on brand pages on social media (Bento and Martinez, 2018).

They focus on style and quality instead of money, and Generation Y's trust and loyalty are reported to fluctuate quickly with trends, fashion, and brand appeal (Reisenwitz and Iyer, 2009; Giovannini, Yingjiao and Thomas, 2015). Generation Z and Generation Y are more actively involved in using digital technology than Generation X and Baby Boomers, according to researchers.

To demonstrate this point, two generations can be compared in terms of their traits and personalities to predict their likelihood of engaging in online shopping. Other criteria, such as the brand's power, may be taken into consideration when assessing attitude toward digital marketing (Reisenwitz & Fowler, 2019). Other researchers have identified values, attitudes, and behavior as significant generational variations (Jackson, Stoel, and Brantley, 2011; Moore and Carpenter, 2008).

2.2.6 The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

It measures how external factors affect consumers' intentions to buy goods and services online in this era of digital technology. The confidence of consumers when they want to buy a product or service online in regard to the security on personal data (privacy) to service providers or entrepreneurs, the marketer online must be able to do marketing in providing positive impacts of doing so (George, 2004).

The implementation of TPB can be influenced by a variety of influencing factors, such as improving the Firms' reputation and being creative in website control that will have an impact on the purchase intention of e-commerce, even though in some cases the three elements of TPB cannot have an impact on purchase intention, such as the absence of behavioral control because it is considered that consumers will feel bored and monotonous (Crespo and Bosque, 2008).

Consumer-generated content is referred to as electronic word of mouth (EWOM). Prospective clients typically use EWOM to determine whether they will trust businesses in electronic transactions (See-To & Ho, 2014).

Dellarocas (2003) demonstrates that consumers' feedback in electronic forums, such as EWOM, can be used to build trust in brands and products. However, there will be both positive and negative EWOM that will help entrepreneurs, as well as the opposite (Filiari, Galati, and Raguseo, 2021).

Potential customers will form favorable expectations about the caliber of the specific goods and services offered when they learn that the EWOM is favorable about certain products sold by a certain Entrepreneur. This optimistic outlook will provide him with the self-assurance to make purchases (See-To & Ho, 2014; Awad & Ragowsky, 2008). On the other hand, if some potential customers hear negative EWOM about the products the company sells, they will form unfavorable expectations about the quality of the company's goods and services, which lowers their trust in both the goods and the company and reduces their likelihood of making a purchase (Lee & Song, 2010).

EWOM is described as moderation in theory, value, belief, and norms which enhances purchase intention (Jaini et al, 2019; and Sun, 2013). The researcher then suggests a study model that can explain how different variables interact in the context of online consumer behavior. Entrepreneurs must work more to build trust online than do consumers or customers.

Figure 3: Modified model from, Melovic, B. et al, (2020)

The independent variable for the model is “**digital marketing management**” and being measured in terms of; Forms of Digital Marketing, Size of the Business, Environment coverage, Cost effectiveness, Brand Perception, Knowledge and Skill, and dependent variable being “**Entrepreneurship and Creativity development**” being determined by Digital Marketing Management, and finally the mediating variables which can facilitate or obstruct the achievement of Digital Marketing towards Entrepreneurship and Creativity development and will be measured in terms of **managerial activities** example, government policies that favour Internet coverage and digital marketing education, Internet users management like, Search Engine optimization and pay per click, international policies that regulate digital marketing and **Influential factors** (attitude, relationship and trust) which attracts the intention and readiness of Entrepreneurs to use Digital technology to develop their business.

3. METHODOLOGY

The following scholars have used Quantitative research methods contrary to this study which only employed qualitative research method under Literature review (Koksal, 2019; Thach, Riewe and Camillo, 2020; Koch, Frommeyer and Schewe, 2020; Hoyle & Smith, 1994; Oni et al, 2014; Hatibu, 2017; Hill, 2015; Chille, 2018; Storey, 2014 and Kimicho, 2020)

3.1 Research Design

The blueprint, plan, or scheme used to develop solutions to the research challenge is referred to as the research design. It indicates the strategy and organization of the inquiry. This study used a descriptive research design, which helps to describe the literature being studied. It focuses on what exists in the study but does not inquire about why. The study used a qualitative research method to analyze the results.

3.2 Area of the Study

As the matter of fact that, Tanzania has 31 Regions, four regions with greater population density, 17 respondents will be taken from each region (Dar es salaam, Mwanza, Kagera and Tabora), but for the remaining regions 16 sample will be taken from each region (Tanga, Arusha, Mbeya, Singida, Dodoma, Iringa, Pwani, Morogoro, Geita, Katavi, Kigoma, Kilimanjaro, Lindi, Manyara, Mara, Mtwara, Njombe, Pemba South, Pemba North, Rukwa, Ruvuma, Shinyanga, Simiyu, Songwe, Unguja North, Unguja Urban West, Unguja South). Figure 2, below (The map of Tanzania) shows clearly all regions of the country where samples will be selected. The country is formally called “**THE UNITED REPUBLIC OF TANZANIA**” because two different nations (Tanganyika and Zanzibar) united together to form Tanzania. Whereas in Tanganyika, there are about 26 regions, and in Zanzibar, there are about 5 regions.

The Map of Tanzania

Figure 04: Retrieved from <https://ontheworldmap.com/tanzania/tanzania-regions-map.html> August 06th, 2024

3.3 Documentary Review

The researcher reviewed different Literatures, and other documents which write about digital marketing and its effects to the Entrepreneurship development in Tanzania especially; initiated policies in digital marketing and Entrepreneurship, and other plans to develop Entrepreneurship through Digital marketing. Also, important writings about different theories related to the study were observed

4. LITERATURE FINDINGS

4.1 Marketing

Managed cost-effective consumer interactions are part of marketing. The most important aspect of marketing nowadays is client pleasure, which is just as important as focusing on products (Kotler et al, 2008). By providing the finest product and avoiding fooling customers for temporary gain, the best companies in the world typically develop a trusting connection with their customers. Providing customers with long-term contentment is the market's common objective (Shipley and Jobber, 2001). A product or service must incorporate extra value in order to have a strong commercial client relationship. The most crucial role of marketing, in the opinion of Drucker, (2001), is to astound the consumer while pursuing profit. Since conventional marketing strategies mainly entailed selling and advertising, it is necessary to conduct research on individual client case studies regarding their needs, goals, and desires.

Currently, the only tool that can be used to develop consumer relationships through marketing is advertising (Kotter and Cohen, 2012). The following lists the marketing process' steps: In order to ensure customer satisfaction, the step takes into consideration both individual demands and market offerings as well as shared understandings between parties. The most fundamental human wants, situated at the base of the pyramid designed by social psychologist Abraham Maslow, are the desire for food and shelter. On top of the pyramid is self-actualization, which is followed by the need for safety, love and a sense of belonging, the desire for self-esteem, and the demands that go along with those wants. This hierarchy can make it easier for the company to situate itself within one of the aforementioned categories and then comprehend the needs of the consumer from that angle. If businesses can successfully prioritize their demands, they will receive favorable feedback from the general public.

Additionally, this would make it easier for marketers to develop their client relationships (Asiegbu et al, 2012). Strategic design and customer-driven marketing: In this step, the marketer should be aware of the customer group that they will be serving with their product and what else they can provide for them. Segmenting the market based on clients should be the initial step in this process. The target search will be easier thanks to the market's segmentation based on grouping. The company must have a proposition value in the market in order to set the product apart from competing products. Samsung any call, as an example (Middleton and Clarke 2001)

Additionally, there are five marketing management concepts that make it easier to develop business ties with the target market. The production idea: This emphasizes mass manufacturing at the lowest possible cost. The product concept: Emphasizes the quality of the product while emphasizing fresh approaches to persuade clients to buy by providing them with a discount or promotion. The marketing idea is to give value to the targeted consumer base after becoming aware of their needs and wants. Social marketing concept: This section focuses on the long-term interests of society as a whole as well as the interests of the consumer. This idea entails remembering the vested interests of society as a whole as well (Lancaster and Withey 2007). Implement the marketing strategies: The marketing strategies are put into action once the target customer's profile has been determined. The 4ps of market strategy implementation; price, product, promotion, and place become critical at this step. The company must combine all 4 ps and create a thorough marketing strategy in order to deliver and communicate with the client. Once the necessary procedures have been completed, it is time to manage client interactions successfully.

It is preferable for the 9 company to carry out market research rather than develop a product that offers higher customer value and would satisfy customers through profitability. When a company practices such management, highly satisfied customers might be developed. These clients will continue to be faithful and make additional purchases in the future, ensuring the company's long-term profitability. In the long run, this profitability can be used to fuel business growth (Shipley and Jobber 2001). As they recognize the limitations of the traditional marketing communication system and the enormous prospects presented by e-marketing, many firms are eager to increase the use of the content marketing tool in their marketing strategy (Baltes 2015). E-marketing is undoubtedly appealing to many businesses as a substitute for traditional marketing, but in order for the marine industry to thrive, it must be used in a particular circumstance (Baltes 2015). Successful marketing starts with understanding your target audience. Good marketers are intimately familiar with their target audience. They have the ability to scrutinize their customers. Understanding internet customers is crucial because their regional and cultural diversity is frequently considerably greater.

Online shoppers also exhibit unique traits and perspectives when looking for information and making purchases. Additionally, a person may act and think differently online than they do offline. E-marketers must therefore keep a closer eye on their online clients overall (Chaffey and Smith, 2008). It is clear that marketing has undergone a significant transformation. From the disciplined, inward-looking period that prioritized the organization to the outward-looking era with a deeper awareness of the market and the individual consumer (Middleton and Clarke 2001). In the current market, market orientation is fundamental information, although many smaller-scale potential businesses have a thorough awareness of the nature of the market's dealings and are sales and production-oriented. Basically, it is a reality that marketing is evolving daily. Whether a company is tiny or huge, the marketing procedure will be the sole important step a product needs before entering the market (Kotler et al. 2008).

Generally, marketing doctrine development moves with the development of technology. Traditionally (in ancient time) it started by development of language when societies of different languages learnt language interchangeably in order to move from one locality to another for better trade. With the favor of development of transport technology, people were able to move far distance for marketing of products, goods or services. Furthermore, the development of printing press technology, it helped people to minimize costs of travel and manpower for marketing, instead marketing possibly done through magazines, letters and written bland papers. After the development of Medias like; Radios and Televisions where these channels could easily reach, marketing was easy. Any new products, goods or services were announced and broadcasted via Radios and Television, during this time of globalization when the world started to join through those means of communication. Now in Digitalization, which is defined by Digital technology, also marketing has shifted into Digital Marketing online and the process can be reach many people at short time and very far distance, example, the use of websites, WhatsApp, twitter, Instagram or Facebook. Through Digital technology marketing is possible even during this era of **COVID-19 PANDEMIC**. So far marketing has passed three phases; Ancient, Globalization and Digitalization phase.

4.2 Digital Marketing

The shift from a conventional marketing strategy to a digital one is driven in large part by globalization and the rise in Internet usage. Through the use of new technological solutions based on Internet services and contemporary information technologies, digital transformation is an evolutionary process that alters our lifestyles and the manner in which we conduct business (Melovic, et al, 2020). Digital marketing, to give it a more precise definition, is the practice of promoting goods and services through online or digital channels such as email, social media, apps, etc. When compared to traditional marketing, digital marketing has an advantage over it in that it allows businesses to analyze marketing initiatives in real time. Smart digital marketers can observe what is working, what is not, and what kind of impact it is having on the general public in this way (Star, 2019; Kimicho, 2020).

Logically, the term "digital marketing" should refer to marketing where communications are transmitted using a media that relies on digital transmission. Digital TV and radio should logically be included in digital marketing, but I've never seen anyone make that assertion (Bird, 2007). Furthermore, marketers should never forget that digital is only one component of marketing. In reality, it makes only a small portion of the promotional mix. Digital marketing in general and social media marketing in particular, are frequently mistaken for being the only means of reaching consumers and a magic bullet that can fix subpar marketing in traditional channels (Charlesworth, 2018). Kingsorth, (2016) the term "digital marketing" originally appeared in the 1990s. Ray Tomlinson sent the first email in 1971, and his invention made it possible for people to begin sending and receiving electronic information via machines. According to Kimicho, (2020) the introduction of database systems in the 1980s gave businesses the room they needed to keep client

data, allowing them to track it more efficiently and changing the dynamic between buyer and seller.

The Archie search engine was developed in 1990 as an index for FTP sites, making 1990 the year that is best remembered as the beginning of digital marketing. Although the idea of CRM (Customer Relationship Management) predates the introduction of digital technology, Charlesworth (2018) notes that the mid- to late 1990s gave rise to the idea that customer intelligence might be managed using those technologies. As a result, during the turn of the century, some businesses spent enormous sums of money on CRM software and/or systems, many of which were marketed as the cure-all for all marketing issues. According to Kingsorth, (2016), search engine optimization (SEO) as we know it today began with the creation of the first web crawler called (Webcrawler) in 1994 and the launch of the first banner advertising in 1993. The current internet era started in 1999 with the birth of Blogger and the accelerated growth of Google. Myspace debuted, Blackberry, a company no longer associated with innovation, introduced mobile e-mail. The origin of social media as we know it today was Myspace.

The phrase "Web 2.0" was first used by Darcy DiNucci in 1999, but Tim O'Reilly popularized it in 2004. Contrary to what the name of the movement might imply, there was no technological revolution with Web 2.0; rather, there was a change in how websites are made. This made it possible for the internet to develop into a social medium, facilitating the emergence of online communities such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Pinterest, Skype, and others. Since social media platforms like Facebook started to attract more users in 2005, businesses in Tanzania have started shifting their marketing strategies to focus on digital channels in order to attract clients and raise brand awareness. The development of new devices suitable for using the internet in the 2010s and market mechanization developments lead to steady, dependable, and pertinent sophisticated advertising approaches. Statistics released in 2012 and 2013 showed that advanced advertising was continuously evolving.

With the growth of online life in the 2000s, for example, Facebook, Twitter, Connected, and Instagram users became profoundly subject to computerized electronic in day-to-day lives; it was evident that advanced advertising was constantly developing. They therefore anticipated an uniform client experience for browsing item data across a variety of mediums. The improvement of encouraging innovation was made possible by the difference in client practices (Kimicho, 2020) SOSTAC, which stands for Situation Analysis, Objectives, Strategy, Tactics, Actions and Control, is a tool that thousands of professionals use to create many types of plans (including marketing plans, corporate plans, advertising plans, and e-marketing plans (Chaffey and Smith, 2008). Where are we right now? is the goal of situation analysis. (In the context of this chapter, this covers the definition of "e" words, user growth, market changes, as well as illustrations of successful and unsuccessful e-marketing), "Where do we want to be?" is what objectives mean. What are the advantages of using the internet, why make the effort, and what is the point? We outline five key goals, causes, or advantages of being online that you should take advantage of. How do we get there? is what strategy refers to. A strategy

outlines how to accomplish the goals. What segments and positioning should drive the total marketing mix and promotional mix, right down to the varied contact strategies for different segments, and which e-tools should be chosen? What stage of evolution and amount of database integration is required? Correcting your e-strategy is essential. There is no point in rowing faster if you are rowing in the incorrect direction, according to Ohmae, (1999). The tactical e-tools and communication mix are reviewed in tactics. Actions refer to project management techniques and action plans, which are crucial abilities. Control examines how to determine whether your online activities are successful and how they might be improved (Chaffey and Smith, 2008)

4.3 Digital Marketing Management

B2B is already far more prevalent online than B2C. General Electric decided to make online transactions totaling \$1 billion in year one, \$3 billion in year two, and then all of its purchases online almost ten years ago. Cisco Systems stated several years ago that they would no longer work with vendors that couldn't accept online orders. Major institutions, like government councils, are also shifting online. For instance, starting in 2005, the Local District Councils of the British Government exclusively purchase their goods and services online (Chaffey and Smith, 2008)

The creation of a digital transformation strategy for the years 2021–2025 has already begun in order to boost digital marketing as much as feasible. The availability and accessibility of telecommunication infrastructures, existing legal frameworks, the growth and accessibility of state administration services, local government, banks, and other financial institutions, adjustments to the educational system and citizen education, and the expansion of the Information Technologies (IT) sector in Montenegro are just a few of the factors that will determine how far digitalization will advance in the country. Each of these disciplines has shown tremendous advancement in recent years. The digital economy is thus a crucial component of digital transformation since it helps businesses become more efficient, productive, and profitable. This makes the process of Montenegro's digital revolution unavoidable, which is why the importance of digital marketing is rising (Melovic et al, 2020)

According to the Tanzania Communication Regulatory Authority's First Quarter Report for 2016, there were roughly 20 million internet users in Tanzania, and 19,862,525 people used the internet overall. As a result, digital marketing in Tanzania is still in its infancy because there are so few internet users and so few people using digital marketing platforms. Internet users in Tanzania are extremely low when compared to the 50 million people who make up the nation's total population (National Bureau of Statistics, 2016). The number of internet users does not accurately represent government efforts to expand communication and internet infrastructure. For instance, the National Information and Communication Technology Broadband Backbone (NICTBB) project was established in 2009 (Kowero, 2012), the National Act was amended in 2015, the Electronic Regulation was established, and the Electronic Regulation protects agents, operators, and consumers during electronic transactions and the ICT policy was adopted in 2016.

Despite these advancements, only a small portion of Tanzanians use digital marketing platforms. According to Kimicho, (2020), customers in Tanzania now have easy access to internet services, which are the main platforms for digital marketing, thanks to the expansion of internet services from urban to rural areas through mobile service providers and the rise of affordable smart phones and tablets. The government's establishment of legal and regulatory organizations like TCRA made it safe and simple for SMEs to use digital marketing strategies into their daily operations.

4.4 Entrepreneurship

The business environment as well as the economy is both thought to have changed as a result of entrepreneurship. Over time, the term "entrepreneur" has come to refer to a person or group of people with the capacity to recognize, assess, and seize on commercial opportunities that exist in their surroundings. A person who can organize resources into a commercial enterprise and manage it with the intention of success is regarded as an entrepreneur or **Youth Entrepreneurs** is a group of people that starts their own business at the young age (15 to 25 years old) (Chigunta, Schnurr, James-Wilson, and Torres, 2005; Hulsink and Koek, 2014).

Success becomes the central concern, the main aim, and the overarching vision of any entrepreneur in this situation. Operationally, entrepreneurship is the capacity or endeavor to establish and run a new business. It is connected to the traits and pursuits of an entrepreneur, for instance, the capacity to see an opportunity and capitalize on it (Mtuka, 2021). We may spend a lot of time discussing entrepreneurship and small company topics. However, when describing entrepreneurship, practitioners tend to have similar understandings. For instance, Thomas, Zimmer and Norman, (1996:52) define entrepreneurship as the practice of applying creativity and innovation to demands and possibilities in the marketplace while being methodical and disciplined in the process.

It entails developing a product or service that addresses the difficulties or demands of clients in addition to applying targeted techniques to fresh concepts and insights. For the majority of urban residents who do not hold a regular paid job, entrepreneurship has been seen as a key source of income. In Tanzania, starting a small business is typically not considered to be problematic. Small businesses can be launched at any time and in any location. The current study, which is based on research findings, questions whether promoting small company entrepreneurship can reduce poverty in Tanzania in the face of rising petty crime rates and administrative obstacles.

The development is said to be on a slippery slope if the complicated and contentious issue involving small businesses is not corrected, if not put to rest. Developing a dialogue portfolio between small company owners and bureaucratic authorities and having authorities create policies that can encourage the growth of small business entrepreneurship are some of the options recommended to resolve the problem (Mtuka, 2021).

4.5 Entrepreneurship Development

The integration of digital technologies into conventional goods and services has provided entrepreneurs with several options to develop fresh value propositions. For instance, West and Kuk, (2016) examined how MakerBot became the market leader in the printing sector by developing an innovative value proposition that combined a printer with an online repository for design files. One viewpoint is looking at digital technology as an enabler that influences business owners' decisions to develop, market, and/or sell new value propositions.

Digital technology can operate as disequilibrating factors that allow for and facilitate different entrepreneurial initiatives (Davidsson, Recker, & von Briel, 2020). Digital technologies can also make one or more of the particular procedures, methods, or acts that form the basis of each entrepreneurial activity possible. For instance, Ceccagnoli et al, (2012) demonstrated that software application platforms give small entrepreneurial businesses a base to market their software products. Participants in the PDW concurred that focusing on digital technologies as results raises a number of research problems, such as the impact of their value propositions' generativity on the development of new entrepreneurial ventures (Jarvenpaa and Standaert, 2018), whether and how institutional fields might affect the procedures and results of entrepreneurial activities (Tumbas et al, 2017), or how the digital objects making up the value propositions of emerging entrepreneurial endeavors might affect pivots throughout emergence (McDonald & Gao, 2019). It would also be intriguing to learn whether some applications of digital technology, such as those involving artificial intelligence, exhibit different growth and scaling dynamics from those of other digital ventures (Iansiti & Lakhani, 2020), or whether and why some applications of digital technology might be more difficult to develop and market than others. The advent of numerous platforms that enable value creation and innovation in business activities with a focus on independent contractors, small businesses, and entrepreneurs is a result of the digitalization of company operations.

Entrepreneurs must consequently acquire new knowledge and creative skill sets in order to survive and thrive in the new computerized economy as a result of digitalization (Jawad et al, 2020; Brem et al, 2021). Applications of the Internet of Things, big data analytics, and blockchain technology have the potential to increase company performance, competitiveness, and productivity (Dwivedi et al, 2021; Sion, 2019; Zahra, 2021). The old marketing comfort zone that marketers have been residing in for so long needs to be left behind. They should stop saying things like, "I don't need social media" and "I don't need a website." When a company's success depended heavily on word-of-mouth, its standing among social groups, and conventional techniques of marketing a few years ago, all of this made sense (Star, 2019). By identifying the many qualities and characteristics of "e-business," "web-based application," "b-webs," and "digital enterprise," Onetti et al, (2012) explain how new, youthful businesses-built internet-based solutions. Building a business model that can generate money is a problem after an entrepreneur has acquired the necessary ICT skills and market orientation to assure survival and profit maximization (Dasgupta, 2013; Oestreicher, Singer & Zalmanson, 2013). According to Javalgi et al,

(2012), the development of information technology created a technological environment that allowed Indian entrepreneurs to engage in innovative activities. The country's context also includes government policies that support small businesses and social and economic integration (exposure to global business opportunities). Thus, generally speaking, local context relates to opportunities that are distinctive to an industry and a nation (Ngoasong, 2015).

Table 2: Retrieved from, NEEP. et al. (2022)

ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT

AREA OF COMPETENCE	ATTITUDES	KNOWLEDGE	SKILLS
Enterprising tendencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for autonomy and independence • Need for achievement • Creativity and innovativeness • Opportunity seeking and taking initiative • Calculated risk taking • Communicative and networking • Integrity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Entrepreneurial traits • Integrity for personal success • Career awareness and opportunity recognition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creativity and problem solving • Communication and networking • Lifelong learning • Personal and social development • Planning and organization • Effective use of technology
Business creation and development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interest in the entrepreneurial career 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business start-up process • Organizing and managing a business 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Business management

The National Economic Empowerment Policy (NEEP), (2004), Youth Development Policy, (200), Education and Training Policy, (1995), National Empowerment Policy, (2008), and Small and Medium Enterprises Development Policy (SMEDP), (2003) all highlight the necessity of incorporating entrepreneurship into the educational system in Tanzania in order to create Entrepreneurship competence, positive attitude towards Entrepreneurship, knowledge and skills as shown in table 2 above. The objective is to promote an entrepreneurial culture in society and equip students with the tools they need

to contribute more effectively to their personal and the country's growth, including increasing their marketability on the job market and generating money.

From basic and secondary schools through teacher preparation colleges, the Ministry of Education and Vocational Training (MoEVT) has incorporated entrepreneurship-related skills into its curricula. The introduction of entrepreneurship as a subject and/or non-formal education to different groups has also been done by several tertiary training institutes (NEEC, et al, 2022).

4.6 Forms of Digital Marketing

The term "internet" refers to the aggregate of all digital platforms, including social networks, media, and mobile (SMS, MMS) systems as well as online radio and television outlets like Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube (Kimicho, 2020). To inform consumers about their items and persuade them to purchase them through websites or mobile applications, e-commerce businesses also use social media (Hajli, 2014) As an illustration, Bird (2007) asked, "Do you have a website? Or do you intend to have one if you're beginning a new business? Yes, if you already have a website, it could be helpful to evaluate it by asking yourself the above questions and comparing the answers. Even better, use them as the basis for your planning if you are preparing to construct a site. A website can be used as a new communications channel to raise awareness, develop a brand, mold client perception, and disseminate special offers, according to (Chaffey and Smith, 2008). A new generation of digital hardware initiatives is being made possible by advancements in digital technologies for prototyping, producing, and commercializing digital hardware. They described how the rise of low-cost electronics development platforms like Arduino or Raspberry Pie and rapid prototyping technologies like three-dimensional (3D) printers or mini-mills enable business owners to produce physical prototypes more quickly and for less money.

Furthermore, by substituting online crowds for conventional finance and market research sources, crowd funding websites like Kickstarter or IndieGoGo enable entrepreneurs to overcome limitations during development according to (Von Briel et al, 2018). Organizations and businesses engage with and grow their customer bases by locating relevant potential clients via digital channels like the Google search engine, email, social media sites, and websites. Additionally, texting, instant messaging, mobile apps, podcasts, electronic billboards, digital televisions, and radio stations are all used in digital marketing. Everything from our website to online branding assets is useful as a resource for digital marketing because we are a company that uses it. There numerous resources that can be used in marketing campaigns, including the corporate website, Whitepapers, e-books, and blog postings Infographics, interactive resources, using social media (Facebook, LinkedIn, Reddit, Twitter, Instagram), received coverage online (public relations, social media, and reviews), Brochures, videos, and branding materials (logos, taglines, graphics, and fonts) all available online (Star, 2019). Even though not every social media platform will be appropriate for every type of business, it's still worthwhile to explore your possibilities. For instance, Facebook and Instagram may be used for nearly any business; they are excellent channels for sharing information, advice, images, and

videos, as well as for asking and answering questions. You may find Twitter, Snapchat, LinkedIn, YouTube, Pinterest, Tumblr, and Foursquare useful after setting up the two crucial accounts. You must determine for yourself which channels are more appropriate for your company. For instance, Instagram is a network for exchanging photos, therefore it will be more effective for companies that rely on images. Businesses that need to emphasize aesthetic appeal in order to generate interest could use Instagram. It's critical to take your target demography into account. In the USA, Instagram has between 133 and 135 million users, more than two-thirds of whom are women between the ages of 18 and 45. In order to access your Instagram account and interact with your followers correctly, you'll also need to maintain a smartphone close at hand (Star, 2019). Although Montenegro does not lag behind other nations when it comes to using digital communication tools like the Internet, social networks, and mobile phone services, it frequently uses these tools insufficiently in other contexts, particularly when it comes to businesses. Since 74 percent of Montenegro's population has access to the Internet, there are greater options to use digital marketing (Melovic et al, 2020). The majority of SMEs in Tanzania, especially in Dar es Salaam and Kinondin, have social media pages set up for their companies. The most popular social media platforms in Tanzania are Instagram, WhatsApp, and Facebook. However, email marketing has also grown to be a crucial tool for business marketing ever since the online world was created. It is essentially there to assist you interact with your audience to promote your brand and increase sales, and it may be considered as a type of direct marketing (Star, 2019; Kimicho, 2020)

4.7 The Influence of Digital Marketing Management

Tanzanian companies, brands, and businesses now use technology differently for marketing than they did in the 1990s and 2000s due to the rise of digital technology (Kimicho, 2020). Things have changed since then. The interaction between suppliers and customers and even between purchasers themselves is the foundation of marketing itself. Consumers are now aware of what other people are saying about a product or brand thanks to the power of digital marketing, in addition to what customers tell them or what a firm says about its brand. Until a customer contacts a salesperson or your organization directly, it is very difficult to determine how many people are truly connecting with your brand through traditional or offline marketing. Finding out when people are most available and watching television or listening to the radio at peak hours is equivalent to doing this. Digital marketing fosters entrepreneurship more readily than traditional marketing, in this regard. Bird (2007) continues, "Whether we are talking about messaging or the internet, this is precisely what digital is, which is why it is unique: easier, cheaper, and quicker. But if it were possible, the internet is "more" distinct than other digital media, thus that is what I want to concentrate on here. Through chat rooms, questionnaires, online logs, and databases, e-marketers can have direct access to consumers' opinions, interests, and purchasing habits. Focus groups small groups of consumers who talk about your product, package, and advertisements can be conducted in chat rooms using a fresh method (Chaffey and Smith, 2008). There are now countless prospective clients online. They prefer to look for companies that have already made a name for themselves. Making the switch to the online world will make things simpler for millions of potential clients who only

need to find you, in addition to your many existing customers. (Star, 2019). Entrepreneurs can use ICT competencies to make technology work for them in order to give creative solutions to the market possibilities they have found (Ashurst et al., 2012). The process of starting a digital enterprise was sparked by the main founder or at least one co-founder acquiring ICT skills through self-study in computer sciences, information management, and web/mobile development or through earning an ICT degree from a university, professional certificate, or professional certification (Ngoasong, 2015). A lot of it can now be done digitally, which makes it much easier for everyone unlike conventional ways, where a company's products or services would be shown at physical sites like showrooms or shops. Through your website or social media account, you can promote your goods and services. This can benefit you in two ways: it can increase interest in your company's products and services and make it easier for customers to interact with you. Once you're online, you'll see that it will be simpler to establish and maintain relationships because it will be less expensive and easier for you both to stay in touch, share your most recent product lines, and gain comments on your offerings. It won't take a lot of time to complete, and there won't be many excursions to interact with customers. You will only need to focus your efforts on one area rather than several, which will make marketing your company and brand much simpler. Due to the fact that the majority of the audience is now present online, the outcomes will likewise be more effective (Star, 2019). Digital marketing management makes it possible for customers to get the information they require more quickly while also saving money for the company. But we need to pause and consider whether all users would like to conduct all of their conversations online (Chaffey and Smith, 2008). Digital marketing is typically thought of as the future of traditional marketing. Managing and regulating more audience interactions than just emails and text messages is the key to success.

4.8 Digital Marketing Management Practices.

One of the elements that determine whether a buyer will buy a product online through or not is their propensity to look for information online. Customers can promptly share information in the accessible electronic media if they are happy or dissatisfied with the service or product they purchased (Mahrinasari, Marquette and Bangsawan, 2017). In the context of buying things online, consumers will also determine the legitimacy of the company online based on customer reviews before making a purchase of products. Because internet reviews can influence online purchase decisions by 20–50%, they are becoming an increasingly essential source of information for consumers (Mathwick and Mosteller, 2017). According to Star (2019), creating an account on websites like Twitter and LinkedIn is an excellent idea. To make it easier to identify you, register using your complete name rather than a separate ID. Also, make sure all of your information is current. The advantage of these websites is that you can choose how much privacy you want and what information is revealed. Customers can express their expertise and opinions on the products and services they have acquired through EWOM on platforms like social media, blogs, online forums, online review sites, and chat sites (Erdomuş and İçek, 2011). EWOM has altered how consumers make judgments when purchasing online (Bickart and Schindler, 2001; Lee, Park and Han, 2008; Xia and Bechwati, 2008). It is not

a good idea to choose a head keyword because you will be spending more money while not getting enough return on your investment. To get a bang for your buck, it is advisable to target a larger number of lower traffic terms for the same amount of money that is spent on a head keyword and target only a few high traffic terms, alongside. Another good idea to include in this strategy is to look for keywords from your own website that customers might potentially use to search for you. Once you find out what your customers are looking for, you will be able to invest your money in more specific keywords and naturally get a higher return (Star, 2019).

Boone and Hendricks, (2014) stated that digital marketing management is a tool that has promoted positive effectiveness, boosts branding, promotes the excellent reputation of businesses, and assists in making it simple to trace the transactions after procurement. Additionally, digital marketing encourages the purchase of less expensive goods because buyers can log in to various websites and compare prices, bringing in new clients on a daily basis all over the world and negating the need to move around in search of new clients. Anyone who wants to purchase something from the businesses places an online order, and the things are delivered to the desired client (Veleva and Tsvetanova, 2020). The web marketer has to consult a professional. In essence, this means that, like all other parts of offline trading, the law is not something that should be (1) taken lightly, (2) ignored, or (3) guessed at. My experience indicates that all three of these situations are rather prevalent, with the dubious strategy of hoping nothing goes wrong and the poor practice being motivated by cost (Charlesworth, 2018). Due to the ability of social networking sites like Facebook and MySpace to provide its user bases with perfectly focused advertising, the appeal of advertising within social networks has always been strong and clear (Mathieson, 2010). The impact of how prospective clients utilize search engines is another factor. The customer enters their desire or requirement in the search box in this case (Charlesworth, 2018). The practice, commonly referred to as "blogola," of paying bloggers, Facebookers, or Twitter users to post about your product or company is the subject of heated debate. Mommy bloggers in particular appear to have been singled out for the behaviors that many regard as particularly prevalent among this category of bloggers: taking free products, gifts, remuneration, or junket vacations in exchange for writing reviews. However, mothers don't necessarily have the monopoly on these things (Mathieson, 2010). Most SMEs in Tanzania spend more than five hours on their social media pages. SMEs with social media profiles typically employ one to four people and have an investment capital of less than five million TZS (Kimicho, 2020). Youth plays role in the development.

4.9 Challenges Faced in Digital Marketing Management

Digital marketing is not a comprehensive marketing strategy, as with anything else. As it develops, there are some difficulties that must be addressed. The only thing that is certain is that digital marketing will eventually reach a larger user base than it does right now. Everyone who works in digital marketing is aware that their material needs to be captivating and appealing therefore this could provide some new issues. However, the issue with most people is that they are genuinely illiterate in the matter. Increasing your

company's positive footprint across all channels is a key component of online reputation management. Many experts in the business are still confused of what methods and tactics to utilize despite the fact that outsourcing the material to a writer or consistently updating your social media accounts with content that may not be very fascinating will get you nowhere in the long run. In a study conducted by Social Media Examiner, it was shown that 96 percent of marketers used social media marketing in some capacity, but that 85 percent of these marketers were unsure of the best tools to utilize (Star, 2019). There are other difficulties besides ignorance about high-quality digital marketing and DCM, such as the following:

Online shoppers live in a risky world of identity theft and privacy invasion; therefore, trust is becoming more and more vital. Online criminal activity will increase if cell phone subscription fraud turns out to be simpler and more lucrative than narcotics trafficking. As telecom fraud in the UK alone approaches £1 billion, criminal gangs actively target mobile operators. Social networking websites can put both an individual and a business at danger of fraud. The public profiles that users upload about themselves in social networking sites can be used to amass personal data (Chaffey and Smith, 2008). Chaffey and Smith (2008) state further: Think about the apprehensions you believe your consumers may experience while considering using the internet. The top security dangers on your list presumably include identity theft, credit card data theft, hackers, hoaxes, malware, SPAM, and big brother mentality. Others worry that a malevolent or criminal hacker will remotely take control of their machine. Additionally, you might have noticed less serious worries like not knowing what to do, fear of becoming lost, worry about having too much information, or worry about having erroneous information. These worries are primarily about diminished client control. Despite these opinions, marketers are anticipated to spend \$1.6 billion annually by 2013 to utilize social networking sites (Mathieson, 2010).

The most crucial concept to comprehend before beginning paid advertising is how keywords truly function because they are one of the most often used paid advertising techniques. One issue with these tools is that they have a propensity to push users to utilize broader keywords in an effort to get more traffic. This method ends up costing more money and being less productive. (Star, 2019). The number of internet users in business in Tanzania remains low, despite the rise in mobile subscribers and other Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools, such as laptops, mobile phones, iPads, and Tablet Computers, as well as current ICT-friendly regulations that promote the use of the internet in business and various activities (Sayodeka, 2012).

This raises several issues, such as what uses for their mobile phones do, they have that go beyond simple voice conversations and text messaging? Although the majority of people text using digital platforms like WhatsApp, Facebook, and Instagram, these digital channels are underutilised in the country's corporate marketing efforts. Perhaps a valid issue is why, given its low cost and extensive reach, the majority of people do not employ digital marketing methods. In Tanzania, 80 per cent of customers spend less time online for marketing and selling transactions and more time on social issues, according to a

study by Kiunsi (2013) at Vodacom Tanzania on electronic transactions and customers' perceptions in Tanzania. This raises issues like: Does Tanzania have a good understanding of digital marketing? Can different businesses in Tanzania rely on digital marketing as the best marketing strategy? To find answers to these inquiries about the influence of digital marketing on company-to-consumer marketing, an empirical study needs to be conducted.

4.10 Ways to Overcome Experienced Challenges in Digital Marketing

You notice text adverts on the main Google search page. These advertisements typically cost less than banner ads and are targeted at clients who are actually looking for a certain product. You must pair text ads with relevant keywords for them to be successful. Google Ads is one of the platforms where you may post your paid adverts (formerly Google AdWords).

The most popular option, it offers the greatest functional system for displaying display and text advertising that are closely related to keywords. Similar to Google, Bing and Yahoo! provide an alternative platform for carrying out the same task. These alternatives may attract less traffic but have more targeted users, which can increase your return on investment. You should be able to maintain track of your investment if you are going to make one. If not, there does not appear to be any point. You should not spend money on paid advertising if you cannot monitor how your ads are doing or where they appear to be falling short. Keeping track of everything in the real world and in real time is more difficult with traditional marketing.

The advantage of the online world, though, is that you can virtually monitor everything in real time without having to move or spend extra money (Star, 2019). Through state-sponsored multimedia resource centers and related ICT training facilities for the youth in universities, colleges, and secondary schools, government policies have also contributed to the aforementioned advancements (Nzèpa & Keutchankeu, 2007; Ndongfack, 2007; Josué, 2007; Wunnava & Leiter, 2009). A number of laws mandated that "imported computers and their accessories were to be duty free for schools" as of 2001 (Josué, 2007: 4), and that 80 percent of nursery and primary schools be furnished with some form of ICT infrastructure, including a national curriculum for ICT instruction (Ndongfack, 2007).

Potential digital entrepreneurs must also cope with issues unique to their country, such as access to capital and protracted bureaucracy for starting and running a new business (Kimbu & Ngoasong, 2013; Pougue & Bernasconi, 2013). To comprehend digital entrepreneurship in Cameroon, it is important to take into account the local context aspects represented by these factors (Ngoasong, 2015). In addition, prospective digital entrepreneurs, who are young aged marketers must deal with difficulties specific to their nation, like slow-moving bureaucracy and financial access (Kimbu & Ngoasong, 2013; Pougue & Bernasconi, 2013). Understanding digital entrepreneurship in Cameroon requires consideration of the local context elements embodied by these criteria (Ngoasong, 2015). Additionally, aspiring digital entrepreneurs must cope with challenges

exclusive to their country, like sluggish bureaucracy and limited financial access (Kimbu & Ngoasong, 2013; Pougue & Bernasconi, 2013). The characteristics of the local context represented by these criteria must be taken into account in order to comprehend digital entrepreneurship in Cameroon (Ngoasong, 2015). According to John Mayo Smith, chief technology officer at R/GA, "software is a medium." "A high-quality user experience and having individuals who understand software are incredibly critical."

All of this is to suggest that an advertising firm without these qualities is just as out of date as Don Draper and the rest of the employees at Sterling Cooper, the fictional company from the television series *Mad Men*, which portrays the early 1960s Madison Avenue advertising scene. The accepted practice at the majority of agencies has been for some time to collaborate with specialists in particular sectors such as social networking, gaming, mobile, or any other discipline in order to "get the best people for the job" (Mathieson, 2010). Integrating online and offline conversations is necessary. The overall positioning and online value proposition defined by the e-marketing strategy should be supported by all communications (Chaffey and Smith, 2008).

Undoubtedly, some would argue that, in an increasingly cutthroat market, it makes more financial sense to pay specialists to carry out tasks as needed rather than adding to costs. However, it should be noted that if your team does not have a solid understanding of the technology, it can be challenging to come up with the original ideas. Who knows what chances you and, by extension, your clients, may miss in the absence of a cross-disciplinary team of in-house professionals? A writer or an art director both are equally important members of the creative team. We also have what we refer to as "connection planners," or account planners, in the room, he adds that makes it easier to do the work "about the experience, about ways to force customers to interact with your brand in a way that they become like free media" by actively pushing the brand on your behalf. Butler claims that his team would never have produced the cool MINI billboards that address drivers by name if they had relied on the outdated Bernbach model. I covered one of these in the previous chapter.

The concept originated during a conversation regarding 3-D glasses for print advertisements. "We can definitely accomplish the same thing with [radio frequency identification] technology, someone in the interactive group said. When a motorist drives by, "it will detect him and it will spit out a message just for him," thanks to RFID chips embedded in MINI key fobs and transmitters installed into billboards. He continues modestly, "We were able to design something that was actually very cool because we have those resources, in-house engineers, technical experts that understood the technology and what's accessible (Mathieson, 2010). Having professionals in the field of digital marketing is crucial, as this argument illustrates. A lot of people have this notion that pleasant comments are paid for. We have what we call "freedom of authenticity" on our platform, he claims. "We pay people regardless of what they say good, terrible, or otherwise. We want them to express openly and honestly held thoughts. We don't permit advertisers to speak for the blogger or to ask them to say things like, "Hey, tell all your friends that this is the best product ever." But it's hard to see a business paying someone

to say bad things about its goods. It can be argued that this type of arrangement is not fundamentally different from "program notes" in television news programs that promote upcoming shows or "a few words from our sponsors" in entertainment programs, despite the fact that my own personal opinion is that brands should avoid pay-for-say transactions with bloggers (Mathieson, 2010). Marketing professionals must keep in mind that businesses with international goals must have a consistent global image. Production should be done with an eye toward the international market, and content rights should be global. As media follows markets, media consumption may become global. An increasingly significant kind of communication is the creation of content that people can distribute through their networks. But as the Universal McCann, (2007) study notes, "it is essential that brands and media organizations think globally when employing these platforms. Conflicting local brand identities and several ones won't work (Chaffey and Smith, 2008).

If Tanzanian businesses make a significant effort to establish a marketing division with a focus on the digital marketing unit, they will benefit because it is simpler to reach the current generation's consumers, who primarily rely on social media for information, at a lower cost than a physical advertisement. By doing this, businesses will be able to boost their revenue through sales and engage with their customers, who can then provide feedback that can be used to determine what the real market wants. Customers will be pleased to see modifications made to the goods and services they purchased from businesses, and businesses will benefit from keeping their customers and generating more cash through increased sales (Kimicho, 2020). In order to promote digital marketing to the Tanzanian community through public and private participation, it is necessary for the Tanzania Communication and Regulatory Authority, the private sector, and other relevant players to come together. A nationwide campaign should be launched to raise awareness of digital platforms, including how affordable and secure they are for businesses (Chille, 2018)

5. CONCLUSION

The study gives enough room for researchers to work on the main issue of the study; Digital marketing management and Entrepreneurship development. The model provided still gives pace for quantitative study. Tanzanian young aged entrepreneurs are hope to implement online information and Word-of-Mouth Influence, building digital legitimacy (Professional presence by registering on platforms like Twitter and LinkedIn—using real names and up-to-date info and empowering EWOM: Electronic Word-of-Mouth), maximizing benefits of Digital Marketing (brand awareness, real time tracking of transactions, transparent price comparison), navigating Legal & Ethical Terrain (presence of experts and beware of "blogola", Leveraging Social Platforms (offering prior precise targeting based on user behavior), answering Challenges in Digital Marketing (Content quality gap, trust & security concerns, digital adoption barriers, overcoming challenges by using targeted text ads: (Platforms like Google Ads, Bing Ads, and Yahoo! Ads) and Track Roi, providing Institutional & Infrastructure Support (IC resource centers etc., providing In-House Expertise & Integrated Strategy, and Call for Cooperation.

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